

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B428

Date: 17 Feb 2009

Take Off: 10:40:00

Landing: 11:00:00

Flight Time: 0h 20m 00s

Campaign: AETIAQ
Operating Area: Cranfield circuit

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Al Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottoway	Directflight	
4	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
5	FTP	Alison Perry	FAAM	
6				
7				
8				
9				
10				
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

The following log sheets are not available for this flight :

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Track plot	No plot available
Xchat	No Xchat on flight
De-brief	No Mission Scientist to write a Sortie De-brief

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	30 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

None recorded?

Sortie Brief

Flight No: B428

Date: 17th February 2009

Guidance Notes for a Field Study at Cranfield Airport, (AETIAQ-Extension), February 2009

Mike Bennett, Project Principal Investigator, Manchester Metropolitan University
February 9th 2008

The fieldwork has been instigated under the AETIAQ project (Aviation Emissions and Their Impact on Air Quality), in turn part of a wider study of the environmental impacts of aviation, OMEGA, which involves a consortium of UK universities (funded through an award from the UK Higher Education Funding Council). The work entails measurements on exhausts from the engines of the BAe146 research aircraft at Cranfield, with this aircraft being made available to researchers through the UK Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements (FAAM). The study was scheduled to take place during the week of 2nd-6th February 2009, but has been delayed by adverse weather. It is now anticipated that the measurements will take place in w/c 16/2/09.

a) Operation of the 146

Eight dedicated apron-to-apron sorties of the 146 are scheduled, each comprising taxi out, takeoff, circle and landing and taxi back to apron. As far as possible, they will take place in succession early in the day, so as to minimize disruption to other airfield users. It may be desirable to split the sorties into two series, with normal airfield operations taking place in between. (See d). In each sortie, the aircraft will spend a short period (several mins) on the runway with engines idling before powering up for takeoff. In the each sortie, there will also be a short period (10 s) when the engines are run at full power with the aircraft static before brakes are released and the aircraft commences its ground run.

A briefing of pilots in the FAAM building by the PI and experimentalists leading each group is required at least 3 h in advance of sorties. [Such a long timescale will not be feasible for an early morning start – in this case we shall have to make a contingent briefing at the end of the previous afternoon].

The Airport and DirectFlight will each endeavour to assign a member of staff to the airside experimentalists in support of these sorties, from 0900, as necessary.

Communication with the aircraft in the sorties will take place via the control tower. The airside experimentalists and control tower will communicate via the assigned member of Airport staff.

The aircraft will taxi out on these sorties at the maximum landing weight, so that high fuel-burn rates may be employed for takeoff without the aircraft developing an acceleration or lift atypical of civil aviation in the early phase of takeoff. This weight will be achieved by taking on a significant fuel surplus.

Supporting data from the onboard flight data recorder will be made available by DirectFlight within a few days of the fieldwork. The data comprise principally the engine fuel-flow rate and fan speed (N1). The pilot will also endeavour to make use of the cockpit FDR event marker, so

that experimenters can establish any offset of recorded FDR times from UTC in subsequent analysis of the data.

Other supporting data from the aircraft will be supplied by FAAM, including high-resolution GPS fixes, atmospheric temperature and humidity and background O₃, NO_x and CO levels.

In the event that the experimental work is extended to include sorties in pursuit of other research projects (see *c* below), an engine power check will be executed on such sorties in support of AETIAQ on the runway prior to takeoff.

b) General airside working

Risk Assessments, Method Statements and a List of Personnel (with contact 'phone numbers) are to be supplied in advance of the study by the project PI to FAAM, DirectFlight Ltd (who fly the aircraft) and Cranfield Airport.

Instruments will be taken airside in vehicles. All experimenters must wear high-visibility jackets when working airside. They should remain close to their vehicles, and can move these only with an Airport escort.

During the dedicated sorties of the 146, the Airport will endeavour to keep any queuing light aircraft close to the main airport buildings, to prevent their exhausts compromising the signal from the exhausts of the 146, and any obstruction of lines of site of the remote instruments (see *c*).

All instruments are to be deployed in the morning and recovered the same day. Vehicles may be stored overnight on campus, to the rear of the FAAM building.

c) Experimental intent

The PI will shoot film footage of the sorties from a camcorder mounted on a tripod on the control-tower first-floor balcony: other experimentalists will locate airside. *In situ* air quality measurements will be made at around 150 m behind the start point: where there may be any exposure to jet blast from the 146, instruments will be secured to the ground (to the satisfaction of the Airport). Remote measurements of air quality will be made by Lidar, with the Lidar being at least 100 m from the runway centreline. Supporting data will be obtained from a met station on the roof of the Lidar vehicle, an extensible mast there being raised to height of 10 m from the ground.

Five possible airside locations have been suggested at which experimental groups could set up: they are listed in the method statement. Two of these locations have already been used in earlier AETIAQ trials. The choice between locations will depend on wind direction and ground conditions. In any event, for the particular measurements we wish to make, we should need light to moderate winds (up to ~10 kt at 10 m), blowing from the SW quadrant. Calm conditions would also be acceptable. We should want moderate to good visibility. In practice, we need daylight to set up, but can then carry on into darkness. The instruments will tolerate no more than a trace of rain.

Care must be taken in setting up equipment so as to minimize the number of generators run, and to site instruments so that their sampling points lie outside any generator exhaust streams. Particular account must be taken of RASCAL, which will be run off its own in-vehicle generator, and which may be sited upwind of the runway so that aircraft exhausts may be studied continuously for the maximum possible time as they drift downwind.

Experimenters need to be in position and to have started their instruments up 2 h before the acquisition of data.

Runways must be dry and winds light for adequate experimental data to be obtained, and sorties should thus be postponed if these conditions are not met.

It would be useful if the experimenters could make some opportune study of the aircraft setting off on sorties in pursuit of other research projects. Deployment of experimental kit airside in these circumstances would depend on the provision of an escort by the Airport, as previously. The extent and duration of such study would depend on the competing demands of the 146 research programme over the AETIAQ week, and experimenters' other commitments.

d) Scheduling over the AETIAQ week

Experimenters will meet at the FAAM building on the first day on site and begin setting up and deploying instruments where possible. A meeting of experimentalists and FAAM personnel should take place that afternoon. Subject to conditions, AETIAQ-Extension sorties will commence on the morning of the following day, with any remaining sorties being flown over two subsequent days. Experimenters will meet with representatives of FAAM, DirectFlight and Cranfield Airport at the FAAM building at 0830 on the day and finalize experimental details, with sorties starting as soon as possible subsequently.

An assessment of the meteorological conditions predicted for the AETIAQ week will be made by FAAM and the PI at the end of the previous week. If the prospect of suitable conditions occurring during the scheduled week appears very weak, it may be necessary to postpone the study further. Otherwise, in the event that conditions prevent completion of the programme on the Wednesday, the experiment will roll forward through the remainder of the week (other FAAM commitments permitting), with conditions predicted over the following 36 hours assessed in a meeting each morning.

Flight:

B428

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B428

Date: 17/02/09

Issues

Instruments

Horace

GIN

Drop outs through flight even when disk not loaded
Thought we were in the atlantic! Drifting west when stationary
No good for first run